

**MODERN SOCIAL MODEL AND LEADER IN NEW UZBEKISTAN FORMATIVE
EXPERIENCES**

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RESUME

This article describes the fact that socio-economic, political-legal, spiritual-cultural processes in modern Uzbekistan are making the activities of leaders more complex and increasing the demands placed on them more than necessary, and on the contrary, it is emphasized that the process of forming the social image of a modern leader is lagging behind the pace of these innovations.

It is emphasized that in order to form a modern leader and improve his social image, it is not enough to rely on the significant experience accumulated in this field in the country, it is necessary to form an ideal leader model, search for young, promising specialists with leadership skills, teach them leadership culture and improve their leadership skills. Therefore, it is scientifically analyzed that without identifying these tasks and ensuring their systematic solution, it is impossible to find a modern leader who would serve the development of the country and the interests of the Motherland.

Basic conceptions: professional mobility, social mobility, modern leader, social image of the leader, ideal leader, democratic management methods, nomenclature of reserve personnel, "mentor-student" system, "young leader", "professional skills", intellectual, moral, legal, political and other characteristics and qualities.

The socio-economic, political-legal, spiritual-cultural processes in Uzbekistan, which are being updated, give a complex tone to the leader's activity and increase the demands placed on him. However, the process of formation of the social image of a modern leader lags behind the pace of these updates. On top of that, a series of factors and problems that hinder the improvement of the leader's social image remain. That is why the changing social reality in Uzbekistan requires a new approach to the issue of training leaders and shaping their social image. Without fulfilling this task, it is impossible to achieve the set goals and solve the problems that have accumulated in various spheres of society. The social image of a modern leader is understood as his virtues and qualities, beliefs, principles he adheres to and his life position. The issue of improving it is not a new issue. At all times, including the thirty-five years since our country gained independence, noteworthy experiences have been accumulated in this regard. In order to achieve a balance between the pace of social reforms and the goal of improving the social image of the leader, it is necessary to analyze and generalize these experiences in detail and determine ways to use them in the future. Because ignoring these experiences will lead to their ineffective completion, disruption of the continuity in the development of knowledge related to the training of modern leaders.

Indeed, the economic reforms, innovations in the social sphere, political and legal changes, and processes of spiritual and cultural revival during the years of independence made the Soviet system and methodology for training leaders irrelevant. Because this methodology, based on the principles of a centralized economy, a one-party political system, social equality, and ideological autocracy, could not form a leader capable of operating in new conditions. The changed reality required a new kind of leader. Therefore, at the initiative of the First President of the country, a holistic model was created that would allow forming such leaders and determining their social image based on the principles of a market economy, universal human values, and democratic

norms. A number of elements of this model have not lost their relevance today. In particular, we believe that the following elements can be effectively used in the new reality:

Firstly, in our country, experience has been formed in establishing a comprehensive system for training managerial personnel and ensuring its regular functioning. As is known, during the years of independence in Uzbekistan, a national model of the system for training managers began to take shape, which includes organizations for improving and retraining personnel, scientific and educational centers, and various training courses. Over the past years, all elements of this model have developed. In particular, the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (in its early stages - the Academy of State and Public Construction) serves as the main element of this system. The establishment of this academy by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 19, 1995 as a scientific center for training managerial personnel, improving their skills, and shaping their social image was a significant step in the formation of a national model for training managers. The Academy has made and continues to make a significant contribution to the training of a new type of managers.

The system for training managerial personnel does not consist only of this academy, of course. During the years of independence in our country, special attention was paid to the organization of faculties, centers, and training courses specializing in training leaders in various sectors. The important feature of such centers is that they allow training leaders based on the specific characteristics, goals, and problems of the economic sectors. For example, for several years now, the Faculty of Training Leaders has been operating at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The faculty approaches the issues of training leaders taking into account the current problems of the industry. According to the Ministry's Information Service, this faculty pays attention not only to improving the professional and combat readiness of future leaders, but also to improving the level of legal knowledge, shaping their social image, and developing leadership skills.

By the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the organization of the activities of the Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers", a structural unit was created in 2020, which is specifically engaged in the training of managers and improving their social image in the healthcare system. This center is not limited to developing the professional qualifications of personnel working in the medical field, but is also engaged in training managers, equipping them with innovative management methods, and forming qualities useful in management activities.

Also, by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On additional measures to further improve the system of retraining and advanced training of reserve personnel for the agro-industrial complex" in 2020, a center for retraining and advanced training of managers and specialists for the agro-industrial complex in the direction of "Agribusiness and Management" was established at the Tashkent State Agrarian University. The center is engaged in the training and advanced training of managers and specialists who can effectively organize their activities in the agro-industrial complex using modern equipment and technologies, including "smart agriculture", digital innovative technologies and information systems. 1

The Main Scientific and Methodological Center, established under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, remains of great importance in the training of managers working in higher educational institutions. The center, on the one hand, pays special attention to the issues of advanced training of persons working in managerial positions, and on the other hand, to the training of reserve personnel.

The above-mentioned centers, institutes, faculties also operate in industry, energy, transport, communications, construction, education, culture, social life and other areas. It should be noted that social reforms in our country have increased the effectiveness of the activities of these

institutions in the past 3-4 years, and most of them have given an innovative character to their activities.

The experiences in our country in establishing a comprehensive system for training managerial personnel and ensuring its regular functioning can be summarized as follows: a) during the years of independence, the foundations of a national model for training managerial personnel were created; the structure of this model has the form of "organizations for advanced training and retraining of personnel - scientific and educational centers - training courses";

b) Over the past quarter of a century, Uzbekistan has developed experience in training managerial personnel based on the specifics of economic sectors;

c) The country's government is constantly improving the structural structures that serve to train managerial personnel and improve their social image.

Secondly, experience has been gained in encouraging leaders to act in accordance with the interests of the people. The First President of the country repeatedly emphasized that reforms are carried out not just for the sake of reforms, but for the sake of people. Therefore, socio-economic reforms in Uzbekistan have always been carried out in the interests of the people. However, by the 10s of the new century, it was observed that managerial personnel were disconnected from real life, accustomed to performing functional tasks not based on the interests of the people, but to reporting to higher authorities. Because of this, various urgent social problems began to accumulate in the localities, which increased citizen discontent. With this in mind, the head of state emphasized: "Today, the most important goal of our life, which is reflected in our Constitution, is the comprehensive provision of human interests, which is an urgent task."¹

To fulfill this task, it was necessary to reorient the activities of leading personnel based on the interests of the people. "In order to ensure human interests," the head of state said, "first of all, it is necessary to communicate with people, with the people, to know their worries, aspirations, life problems and needs well."² For this purpose, first the Prime Minister's electronic reception on the Internet was created in our country, and later the virtual reception of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In the first months of its establishment, more than 218 thousand citizens addressed it with various problems.³ This indicates that in recent years, an absolutely effective and original system has been created in Uzbekistan, which has no analogues in other countries, encouraging leaders to act in accordance with the interests of the people.

The new system has made it possible to identify many of the people's problems. "Here's what people are asking about," the head of state said. "First of all, they are asking about removing bureaucratic obstacles in various areas, canceling numerous departmental instructions that contradict the law, allocating bank loans with optimal interest rates, eliminating illegal inspections of entrepreneurship, and improving the activities of law enforcement agencies."

At the same time, our population is also receiving many requests for housing construction, utilities, transport and trade services, energy supply, and improving the condition of roads."¹ In accordance with the insistent demand of the head of state, the activities of the country's leadership were directed to eliminating these problems. Thus, by identifying and eliminating urgent social problems, conditions were created to ensure harmony between leadership activities and the interests of the people.

In the conditions of a modernizing Uzbekistan, the experiences of encouraging leaders to act in accordance with the interests of the people can be summarized as follows:

a) An unparalleled system has been formed in Uzbekistan that allows ensuring harmony between leadership activities and the interests of the people;

b) the new system has made it possible to implement the principle that "the people should serve the state bodies, not the state bodies"².

These experiences will create a foundation for the effective work of leadership personnel in the future for the development of the country and the interests of the people.

The conclusion is that the issue of improving the social image of a modern leader requires relying on the experience accumulated in recent years. Only then will the development of knowledge related to the training of leaders be ensured from a historical point of view. The results of the research conducted indicate that during the years of independence, significant experience has been gained in our country in establishing an integrated system for training leaders and ensuring its regular operation, creating scientific and methodological sources for training leaders, subjecting the activities of leaders to clear principles, establishing control over them, and directing them towards the interests of the people. We believe that these experiences will play a role in the future as a theoretical, methodological and practical basis for improving the social image of the leader, developing a modern management model based on effectiveness in the management system of New Uzbekistan, methodologically coordinating its implementation, and developing the potential of personnel in all areas to perform relevant tasks and achieve target indicators.

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